

Data management plan (DMP)

Data quality a strategic consideration for scaling AI

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	14/12/2023	First version of DMP – created for start of project

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FWF Data Management Plan (DMP)

Guidance and Template

These guidelines are intended to be used as a guidance in the creation of a data management plan for an approved FWF project. This document is based, with minor changes, on the [RDM Guidance for Researchers](#) of Science Europe.

Please answer all the questions in the second column and address the items in the third column. The DMP template can be found at the end of these guidelines, and further information is available in the [DMP Evaluation Rubric](#).

Guidance

I General Information		
<p>I.1 Administrative information</p>	<p>This project is a master thesis project and focuses on analysing data quality management in manufacturing industry. The project is supervised by the Royal Institute of Technology and sponsored by Columbus Global.</p> <p>The principal investigator is: Emil Sörqvist, emilsor@kth.se, ORCID iD: 0000-0003-0530-7442</p> <p>This DMP is version v1.0 and will be updated when licences, data structure or other circumstances make the information in this document obsolete.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide the relevant grant information. - Consider regular updates of the DMP.
<p>I.2 Data management responsibilities and resources</p>	<p>The principal investigator, Emil Sörqvist, will be responsible for data management and revisioning the DMP. Resources used in this project will be KTHs GitHub for storage of project data and version control. Due to the size of this project no big costs are associated with the data management.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indicate who is responsible for implementing the DMP, and for ensuring it is reviewed and, if necessary, revised. - For collaborative projects, explain the co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners. - Explain how the necessary resources (for example, time) to prepare the data for sharing/preservation have been costed in. Carefully consider and justify any resources needed to deliver the data. These may include storage costs, hardware, staff time, and repository charges.

II Data Characteristics		
<p>II.1 Data description and collection or re-use of existing data</p>	<p>New data will be produced in this thesis project through semi-structured interviews and a survey. A pre-study approach is utilized where the semi-structured interviews will be carried out. Interview data will be in audio format and later transcribed in doc format. This data can be expected to constitute the biggest part of our data 5-10gb. The survey data will be collected in a CSV format.</p> <p>Companies participating in the study will provide data from their organisations. The provided data will be process descriptions, organizational charts, and data pipeline documentation. This data will mainly be in formats of pdf and doc. The usage of this data will be constrained by the licenses that protect this data. Access will be limited to the principal investigator. The number of data files will be around 30-60.</p> <p>When creating data this project will do the transcriptions in word due to the widespread usage and possibilities for easy sharing. Audio will be saved in MP3 format due smaller file sizes and its widespread use.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain which methodologies or software will be used if new data are collected or produced. - State any constraints on re-use of existing data if there are any. - Explain how data provenance will be documented. - Give details on the kind of data: for example, numeric (databases), textual (documents), image, audio, or video. - Give details on the data format: the way in which the data is encoded for storage, often reflected by the filename extension (for example, pdf, xls, doc, txt, or rdf). - Justify the use of certain formats. For example, decisions may be based on a preference for open formats, standards accepted by data repositories, widespread usage within the research community, or on the software or equipment that will be used. - Give preference to open and standard formats as they facilitate sharing and long-term re-use of data (several repositories provide lists of such 'preferred formats'). - Give details on the volumes (they can be expressed in storage space required (bytes), and/or in numbers of objects/files).
III Documentation and Data Quality		
<p>III.1 Metadata and documentation</p>	<p>All the audio files will have a corresponding transcription document linked to it. In this document more information is given about the time, date, and the place where it was recorded. The names and position of the interviewee and the interviewer will also be noted.</p> <p>The survey data will be supplemented with a document that shows the survey questions and how each question is quantified.</p> <p>A description of the methodology will also be found in the thesis report. The readme file on</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data. - Use community metadata standards where these are in place (see Digital Curation Center or RDA Metadata Directory). - Consistent, well-ordered research data will be easier to find, understand, and re-use. Indicate how the data will be organised during the project, mentioning for example conventions, version control, and folder structures. - Consider what other documentation is needed to enable re-use. This may include information on the methodology used to collect the data, analytical and procedural information, definitions of variables, units of measurement, and so on. - Consider how this information will be captured and where it will be recorded for example in a database with links to each item, a 'readme' text file, or lab notebooks.

	dataset level will also provide additional information about the data.	
III.2 Data quality control	A lot of the data is of a qualitative nature, e.g. recordings of the interview. To make sure that the transcript and analysis of the interview is accurate the interviewee will be asked after the interview when the results are compiled to peer review it. Data collection in the survey will be done and stored. Non-complete answers will be kept but not analysed and cleansed later.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain how the consistency and quality of data collection will be controlled and documented. This may include processes such as calibration, repeated samples or measurements, standardised data capture, data entry validation, peer review of data, or representation with controlled vocabularies.
IV Data Storage, Sharing, and Long-Term Preservation		
IV.1 Data storage and backup during the research process	<p>Data and metadata will be stored in GitHub during the project. GitHub is the version control solution and collaboration platform this project uses. Data will also be backed up automatically every week at KTHs local server. In case of an incident files can be accessed from KTHs database using a KTH login and a VPN.</p> <p>The right to assign access rights to the data will be principal investigator, Emil Sörqvist's. Access to the GitHub repository will be given to the KTH supervisor and sponsor at Columbus Global.</p> <p>Before collecting data from the interviews all interviewees need to sign an agreement to participate in this research and provide data that will be used and published in the thesis. After the projects termination the interview data will be anonymized.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe where the data and metadata will be stored and backed up during research activities and how often the backup will be performed. It is recommended to store data in least at two separate locations. - Give preference to the use of robust, managed storage with automatic backup, such as provided by IT support services of your home institution. Storing data on laptops, stand-alone hard drives, or external storage devices such as USB sticks is not recommended. - Explain how the data will be recovered in the event of a technical incident. - Explain who will have access to the data during the research and how access to data is controlled, especially in collaborative projects. - Explain which institutional data protection policies are in place. - Consider data protection (e.g., default technical security measures of the home institution), particularly if your data is sensitive (for example, containing personal data or politically sensitive information). Describe the main risks and how these will be managed during the project.
IV.2 Data sharing and long-term preservation	Data will be shared publicly as far as possible in this project. Interview data and survey data will be available during the project. Survey and interview data will be under a CC license. Data will be available in the KTH GitHub, gits-15.sys.kth.se/emilsor/DQThesis. Data to keep long term is the survey data and will be stored for 10 years at GitHub.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain how and when the data will be shared. Consider the FWF's Open Access policy on research data. Immediate open access to research data is mandatory for data underpinning research papers, unless there are legal, ethical, or other reasons not to do so. Explain such reasons where applicable. - Explain how the data will be discoverable and made available for re-use, addressing the choice of repository, the persistent identifier (e.g., DOI), and the licence to use (see "How to License Research Data"). When choosing a repository, follow the Science Europe Criteria for the selection of trustworthy repositories and use http://www.re3data.org/ to search for repositories.

	<p>To access and read the data no specific tools are needed except Microsoft word and excel to open the CSV and doc files.</p> <p>The data given from companies will likely have different legal restrictions on it and cannot be shared openly during the project. After the end of the project this data will be destroyed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indicate who will be able to use the data. If it is necessary to restrict access or to apply a data sharing agreement, explain how and why. Explain what actions will be taken to overcome or to minimise restrictions. - Describe whether potential users need specific tools to access, interpret, and (re)-use the data (e.g., codes, algorithms). Consider the sustainability of software needed for accessing the data. - Indicate what data must be retained or destroyed for contractual, legal, or regulatory purposes. - Outline how it will be decided what data to keep and what data not to keep. Describe the data to be preserved long-term and give information on how long and where the data will be retained.
V Legal and Ethical Aspects		
V.1 Legal aspects	<p>As mentioned earlier data given from the companies where the case studies were carried out will be subject for ownership of that company. The legislation will likely vary from data file to data file. The principal investigator and the supervisor at KTH will be given legal rights to view these documents.</p> <p>All the participants in the interviews will need to sign a informed consent that their role/ title and company name will be published as part of the study. Their data will not be anonymous until the end of the project.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain who will be the owner of the data, meaning who will have the rights to control access. - Make sure to cover the matters of rights to control access to data for multi-partner projects and multiple data owners, in the consortium agreement. - Indicate whether intellectual property rights (for example, Database Directive) are affected. If so, explain which and how will they be dealt with. - Indicate whether there are any restrictions on the re-use of third-party data. - Ensure that when dealing with personal data, data protection laws (for example, GDPR) are complied with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gain informed consent for preservation and/or sharing of personal data. ▪ Consider anonymisation, pseudonymisation, or encryption of personal data for preservation and/or sharing (truly anonymous data are no longer considered personal data). ▪ Explain whether there is a managed access procedure in place for authorised users of personal data.
V.2 Ethical aspects	<p>It must be made clear that the interviews will be used in the report and that the company names will be used in the report. No names of the interviewees will be used only title/role will be used in the report.</p> <p>All interviewees will be asked to sign a to provide informed consent. The survey will also be anonymous but data will be collected about the respondents company and role he/she has in the company.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consider whether ethical issues can affect how data are stored and shared, who can see or use them, and how long they are kept. Demonstrate awareness of these aspects and respective planning. - Follow the national and international codes of conducts and institutional ethical guidelines, and check if ethical review (for example, by an ethics committee) is required for data collection in the research project. - Consider "Ethics for researchers" published by the European Commission or "The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity".

Template

I General Information																							
I.1 Administrative information	<p>PI:</p> <p>FWF grant information:</p> <p>DMP version: [Nr.1], [14 12 2023]</p>																						
I.2 Data management responsibilities and resources	<p>Person responsible for data management and DMP: Emil Sorqvist, emilsor@kth.se, ORCID iD: 0000-0003-0530-7442</p> <p>Co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners:</p> <p>Resources costed in for RDM: There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="441 592 2087 783"> <thead> <tr> <th>Cost name</th> <th>Cost type</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Unit</th> <th>Value</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="4">Estimated total costs</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Additional description (if required):</p>					Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value						Estimated total costs				0			
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II Data Characteristics																							
II.1 Data description and collection or re-use of existing data	<p>Produced datasets:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="441 979 1733 1254"> <thead> <tr> <th>dataset ID</th> <th>title</th> <th>type</th> <th>format</th> <th>estimated volume</th> <th>contains sensitive data</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>P1</td> <td>DQThesis_Interviews</td> <td>Standard office documents, Audiovisual data</td> <td>Doc, MP3</td> <td>20 GB</td> <td>yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>P2</td> <td>DQThesis_Survey</td> <td>Structured text</td> <td>CSV</td> <td>1 GB</td> <td>no</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Reused datasets:</p>					dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data	P1	DQThesis_Interviews	Standard office documents, Audiovisual data	Doc, MP3	20 GB	yes	P2	DQThesis_Survey	Structured text	CSV	1 GB	no
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	dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
	R1	DQThesis_Company_Specific_Data			yes
<p>Methods and software used for data generation and reuse</p> <p>The interviewed companies will give access to data from their internal documentation. Descriptions of processes and data pipelines will be accessed through internal enterprise storage or transferred to the principal investigator.</p>					
III Documentation and Data Quality					
III.1 Metadata and documentation	<p>Data organisation, metadata, and documentation:</p> <p>The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined “DQThesis_<dataset>_<name>”. Version control is automated.</p> <p>As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at dataset level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.</p> <p>Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.</p> <p>A far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.</p> <p>The data will be provided in raw form with transcriptions of the interviews. The analysis techniques will be presented in the thesis paper. Used scripts for creating visualisations of the survey data will be stored and documented at gits-15.sys.kth.se/emilsor/DQThesis.git</p>				
III.2 Data quality control	<p>Data quality control:</p> <p>The following data quality checks will be done, repeated samples or measurements, and peer review of data.</p>				
IV Data Storage, Sharing, and Long-Term Preservation					
IV.1 Data storage and backup during the research process	<p>Storage and backup facilities:</p> <p>For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.</p> <p>P1 (DQThesis_Interviews), P2 (DQThesis_Survey), R1 (DQThesis_Company_Specific_Data) will be stored in KTH Github.</p> <p>Data security and protection of sensitive data:</p> <p>We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies. In this project there will be sensitive data in dataset P1 (DQThesis_Interviews), and R1 (DQThesis_Company_Specific_Data). To ensure that storage and transfer of sensitive data is safe, additional security</p>				

measures such as individual log-in and password is taken. Only The author of the thesis, the supervisor at KTH, and Columbus will be authorised to access sensitive data.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	no access
P2	writing	reading only	no access
R1	writing	reading only	no access

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

IV.2 Data sharing and long-term preservation

Data publication and access conditions:

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Restricted		2024-04-14			CC BY 4.0
P2	Open		2024-04-14			CC BY 4.0

Methods or software needed to access and use data: The data from the survey will be accessible as CSV files.

Description of protocol to access restricted data: To get access to the interview data the person needs to contact the author of the thesis, emilsor@kth.se. Consent and access will be given in written form. The person seeking access will only be provided with transcriptions of the interviews that has been anonymized.

Long-term preservation and deletion of data:				
dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users	
P1		10 years	Decision makers in industry and researchers	
P2		10 years		

Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted:

dataset ID	kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person
R1	DQThesis_Company_Specific_Data	End of project	Company ownership	Emil Sörqvist

V Legal and Ethical Aspects

V.1 Legal aspects	<p>Personal data:</p> <p>In this project, we will process personal data (see section 1a). P1 (DQThesis_Interviews), and P2 (DQThesis_Survey) will contain personal data. We will ensure compliance with data protection laws, by gaining informed consent for processing personal data, and by anonymisation of personal data for preservation and sharing. When anonymising the interview data company name, role/title and years worked at the company will remain.</p> <p>Intellectual property rights and ownership:</p> <p>Legal restrictions on how data is processed and shared are specified in the confidentiality agreement. The restrictions relate to datasets R1 (DQThesis_Company_Specific_Data). The legal restrictions are based on the following: Internal data from the interviewed companies will be analysed in the project. This data or parts of this information is business sensitive.</p> <p>The owner of this data will be the interviewed company and they control the access to this data. has rights to the produced data and controls access.</p>
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V.2 Ethical aspects	Ethical issues: Ethical issues in the project have been identified and discussed with the Research Ethics Coordinator at TU Wien (www.tuwien.at/research-ethics). They are described in detail in separate documents.
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